

Table 2. Summary of grain quality characteristics of promising varieties in the International Fine Grain Aromatic Rice Observational Nursery, 1996 wet season.

Variety	Origin	HRR ^a (%)	KL (mm)	L/B	Alk val.	WU (mL)	VER	KLAC (mm)	ER	AC (%)	Scent	Grn. chalk
<i>Long slender group</i>												
DR28	Pakistan	61.0	7.38	3.53	7.0, 7.0	310	4.0	13.2	1.82	26.1	3	VOC
DR31	Pakistan	61.8	6.88	3.31	7.0, 7.0	230	3.8	11.3	1.64	26.4	2	VOC
Domsiah	Iran	52.0	6.80	3.54	4.8, 5.0	290	4.7	13.2	1.94	18.2	3	VOC
PK1379-9-1-1	Pakistan	56.3	6.62	3.15	6.0, 6.0	250	4.3	13.2	1.99	19.0	3	VOC
PK165648-2-2-1	Pakistan	60.0	6.50	3.16	7.0, 7.0	270	4.3	12.2	1.88	22.6	2	A
DM 38	Pakistan	64.2	6.53	3.27	3.1, 3.1	130	4.0	12.1	1.85	21.4	3	OC
<i>Long bold group</i>												
Azucena	Philippines	64.8	6.39	2.88	4.2, 3.2	130	4.0	11.3	1.77	20.9	2	OC
<i>Short bold group</i>												
ARC 11554	India	69.7	4.17	2.12	5.0, 4.3	110	4.3	7.6	1.82	21.8	2	A
Tulsimanjari 14-2	India	67.5	4.20	2.19	3.0, 3.0	100	4.3	7.9	1.88	21.0	2	A

^aHRR = head rice recovery, KL = kernel length, L/B = length/breadth, Alk val. = alkali value, WU = water uptake, VER = volume expansion ratio, KLAC = kernel length after cooking, ER = elongation ratio, AC = amylose content, scent: 3 = strong, 2 = moderate, Grn. chalk = grain chalkiness: A = absent, VOC = very occasionally present, OC = occasionally present.

Seventeen varieties had the most desirable AC range of 20-25%, and six varieties showed intermediate GT. Three varieties—ARC11554, Azucena, and Basmati 385—possessed both intermediate AC and GT. Except for PK1385-6-3-1-2, all other varieties had an aroma, which is the typical characteristic of basmati rice.

With excellent phenotypic acceptability, DR28 and DR31 (Pakistan) had >60% HRR, moderate to high KL and KLAC, and slightly higher AC (Table 2). Domsiah (Iran) was another variety that possessed all the quality traits in a desirable range, with a slightly low AC. Other varieties from Pakistan having moderate to high

HRR, KL, and KLAC coupled with good phenotypic acceptability are PK1379-9-1-1, PK1756-49-2-2-1, and DM38. With the emphasis now shifting toward the development of dwarf short-grained aromatic rice for domestic and export purposes as well, Azucena, ARC 11554, and Tulsimanjari 14-2 may also be used as donors depending on the objectives. ■

Effect of bran removal on oil recovery

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For the past two decades, India has been meeting a shortage of oils by importing this commodity at extremely high costs in terms of foreign exchange. The demand for vegetable oils in the year 2000 will be 8.75 million t. To augment oil and fat resources in India, rice bran oil needs to be made available to the maximum extent.

Experiments were conducted with two popular and common varieties of parboiled rice: coarse (UPR79) and fine (Basmati) rice grown in the Tarai region of Uttar Pradesh, India. The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of bran removal on oil recovery. Clean rice samples were collected from a commercial rice mill.

Effect of bran removal on degree of polish and oil recovery of rice bran.

Time of milling (s)	Basmati ^a			UPR79		
	D _p (%)	O _r (%)	W _g (g)	D _p (%)	O _r (%)	w _g (g)
0	0	0	0.02299	0	0	0.02145
10	3.33	15.70	0.02146	2.75	14.57	0.02054
20	3.94	18.57	0.02055	3.49	14.90	0.02032
30	5.08	19.25	0.02010	4.46	15.56	0.01962
40	6.32	19.52	0.01956	5.06	16.55	0.01732
50	7.02	20.91	0.01909	5.34	17.46	0.01730
60	7.83	20.91	0.01801	5.81	17.90	0.01676
70	8.13	19.95	0.01755	6.25	17.02	0.01615
80	8.51	19.51	0.01760	6.56	16.34	0.01610
90	8.84	18.76	0.01700	6.97	15.72	0.01600
100	8.94	17.60	0.01620	7.18	15.58	0.01536
110	9.05	17.07	0.01618	7.57	15.07	0.01480

Statistical parameters of $O_r = aD_p - bD_p^2$

Variety	a	b	r	SEE
Basmati	6.367	0.4859	0.999	0.721
UPR79	6.348	0.5822	0.991	0.699

^aD_p = degree of polish on brown rice basis, %; O_r = oil recovery of rice bran, %; W_g = weight of one grain, g; r = correlation coefficient; SEE = standard error of estimate.

The moisture content of collected samples of UPR79 and Basmati was determined by the oven method. Both varieties had an average moisture

content of about 14%. The collected rice samples were shelled and milled/polished via a Satake rice sheller and polisher. Milling time varied from 0 to

110 s, with an interval of 10 s to control bran removal (degree of polish). The degree of polish ranged from 0 to 9.05% and 0 to 7.57% for Basmati and UPR79 rice, respectively. The collected bran at the end of each interval of milling was used to extract the oil using Soxtec HT.

The table shows the effect of time of milling on the degree of polish and oil recovery of bran. Oil recovery ranged from 15.70 to 20.91% for Basmati and 14.57 to 17.90% for UPR79. The maximum oil content was observed at 10 s milling time, for which the degree of polish was 3.33% for Basmati and 2.75% for UPR79. For both varieties of rice bran, the oil recovery starts increasing from 0 to 60 s time of milling samples of bran and then decreases from 70 to 110 s. The oil content of both varieties was maximum at 7.83 and 5.81% degree of polish for Basmati and UPR79, respectively. Weight of a rice grain at the end of each time of milling is shown in the table.

Various mathematical models were tested for their suitability (least error prediction criterion) to describe the oil recovery (O_r) of bran. The following model was found to correlate the experimental observations satisfactorily:

$$O_r = aD_p - bD_p^2$$

The coefficients a and b and statistical parameters of the equation are given in the table. In view of the high r value and low associated error, the above model has been accepted and tested for validity in commercial rice mills. ■

Jaymati, a high-yielding summer rice variety with good grain quality for Assam

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Flooding causes a heavy decrease in winter rice area, with a resulting

decline in production and productivity in the state of Assam. There is therefore scope for bringing chronically flood-affected and waterlogged winter rice areas under summer (boro) rice cultivation. With the increase in irrigation facilities, summer rice area is increasing fast. But a suitable summer variety for flood-affected areas must be of 160-170 d duration so that it can be harvested before the onset of flooding in mid-May.

We therefore developed Jaymati (TTB 103-2), a medium-tall (130 cm) rice variety from the cross Jaya / Mahsuri by the pedigree method of breeding. Jaymati is photoperiod-insensitive and suitable for transplanting in summer and autumn, and has well-exserted panicles and a brownish husk. Grains are awnless and medium in size. The variety has a 1,000-grain weight of 20.2 g. Kernels are white, with a nonglutinous endosperm. The

length and width of the kernels are 6.34 mm and 2.16 mm, respectively. Milling recovery is 66.5%. Jaymati is moderately resistant to bacterial blight, gall midge, and stem borer.

The duration of Jaymati from seed to seed is 170 d for summer and 130 d for autumn and winter rice. The variety's good grain quality gives it an advantage for growing autumn rice. Most autumn varieties grown by Assam farmers have coarse grains. Because farmers need a Mahsuri type of grain for autumn cultivation, some farmers grow Mahsuri in autumn. But because its longer growth duration is not suitable in that season, Jaymati would be a better choice.

Jaymati was tested at several locations throughout the state and it performed well as a summer crop (see table). It was recommended for summer cropping in the Central and Brahmaputra Valley zone of Assam by the state for 1996. ■

Yield performance of Jaymati.

Location	Year	Season	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
			Jaymati	Jaya/local	LSD (0.05)
RARS, Titabar	1989	Autumn	3.4	3.0	0.70
	1990	Autumn	4.8	3.5	1.00
	1991	Autumn	3.3	3.9	1.25
	1991	Winter	4.4	4.0	1.70
	1991	Summer	3.2	2.2	0.30
National trial					
AICRIP (JET13316), 1991, winter					
Chiplima	-	-	7.7	7.0	1.26
Sindri	-	-	6.0	5.3	1.35
Masodha	-	-	4.3	4.2	0.50
Kanpur	-	-	3.7	2.9	0.26
Rajpur	-	-	2.8	2.8	0.72
Titabar	-	-	4.4	4.0	1.72

Location	Year	Season	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)			
			Jaymati	Mahsuri	Jagliboro	LSD (0.05)
RARS, Shillongani, Nagaon						
	1991-92	Summer	7.3	6.3	4.0	0.65
	1992-93	Summer	6.9	6.2	4.0	0.52
	1993-94	Summer	6.4	6.2	4.0	0.81
On-farm testing						
	1994-95	Summer				
Tokowbari	-	-	6.2	3.2	-	-
Dablongati	-	-	4.0	3.2	-	-
Bengenati	-	-	3.3	3.2	-	-
Bahuabheti	-	-	6.0	4.8	-	-
Pooled average over season and year						
	Autumn		3.83	3.40		
	Winter		4.76	4.31		
	Summer		5.41	3.58		
	Overall		4.88	3.84		